

Assessment of Crop Combination Pattern for Sustainable Development in Agriculture use of Geospatial Technologies in Shirur Tehsil, Pune District, Maharashtra

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Abstract

Sustainable agriculture consists of environmental-friendly methods of farming that allow the production of crops or livestock without damage to human or natural systems. It involves preventing adverse effects to soil, water, biodiversity etc. By making maximum use of technology in agriculture, India can achieve significant success in the agricultural sector. For this purpose, the development of agriculture is extremely important within the concept of Developed India promoted by the Government of India. From this perspective, it is necessary to study the agricultural sector through a scientific approach.

In agriculture, it is important to examine the interrelationship between factors such as cropping patterns, water availability, land, soil, and climate. A detailed and systematic study of these elements helps in understanding the crop composition and agricultural practices of a particular region.

A similar micro-level study has been conducted for Shirur Taluka, focusing on its cropping pattern. The information regarding the cropping pattern in this region is presented as follows. It can take the form of double-cropping, in which a second crop is planted after the first has been harvested, or relay cropping, in which the second crop is started amidst the first crop before it has been harvested. All Twelve types of crop combinations have been identified during 2001-2 to 2011-12 for Shirur Tahsil. The villages and area under each crop combination are shown in the table given below. During 2001-12 two crop combination was found in area hectors 3988, and area in 3.93 percent. In 2011-12 2 two crop combination is hectors 6505. The area of three crops combination reduced in 2000-01 (33.15 percent). And 2011-12 in which seven villages area in 5052 hectors, and 5.22 Present. The area of four crop combination was reduced in 2000-01 (19.39 percent). And 2011-12 in which 18 village's area in 18223 hectors and 18.84 at present it. The twelve

crop combination is reduced in 2000-01 (18.47percent). And in 2011-12, it was found in 14 village's area in 16460 hectores and 17.02 present.

Developed India and agricultural practices are closely related. Changes in agricultural practices and the implementation of geographically appropriate measures are essential to increase agricultural production. By using geospatial technologies and their unique applications, it is possible to contribute significantly toward achieving the vision of a developed India by 2047. In an agriculture-dominated country like India, the development of agricultural technology and new research-based knowledge can help in conducting a detailed study of cropping patterns and farming systems. Through the use of advanced geospatial technologies and scientific analysis, it becomes possible to improve agricultural productivity and planning. This will certainly help in fulfilling the dream of a developed India by 2047.

Keyword: Geospatial Technologies, Crop Combination, Sustainable Development, Viksit Bharat,

Introduction

The Brundtland Commission Report, Our Common Future, popularized the notion of sustainable development as “development that meets the need of the present without compromising the ability for future generation to meet their own needs. (WCED 1987).Crop Combination analysis in geographical studies has gained momentum and its importance is increasing day by day. The study of crops on regional scale must take into consideration the combinational analysis and the relative position of crops. Such analysis would ultimately minimize the change of oversimplified generalization. Combination studies are fruitful in many ways: firstly, they provide an adequate understanding of individual crop geography. Secondly, the combination is in itself integrative realities that demand definition and distribution analysis, and lastly crop combination regions are essential for the construction of still more complex structure of vivid agricultural region.

Study Area

Shirur tahsil of Pune district in Maharashtra state has been selected for the proposed work. The tahsil comprises of 118 villages and one urban center. The absolute geographical location of study area can be expressed as from 18°49'00" N to 19°34'00"N latitude and 74°22'00" E to 75°03'00" E longitude. Shirur City is located on the boundaries of the Pune and Ahmednagar districts on the banks of the River Ghod. The town Shirur is also known as Ghodnadi. Shirur has a significant historical and cultural reference.

The area of Shirur tahsil extent form north to south 24 km and 50 km from east to west. Agriculture is the main occupation of this region. The study area shows low rainfall with high variability. Average rainfall in the district is 600 mm to 700 mm.

Objectives

- To study the cropping pattern and geography correlation
- Find out status of Crops in Study Area.
- To assess Crop Combination Pattern.
- Use of Geospatial Technologies.

Methodology

The following methodology was adopted to assess crop combination:

Crop combination Method (Weaver's 1954) Formula-

$$\text{Variance} = \frac{\sum d^2}{n} \quad \text{Standard Deviation} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum d^2}{n}}$$

Where, d = the difference between actual crop % in a given unit and the % in the theoretical distribution.

n = the numbers of crops in a given combination

Crop Combination in Shirur Tahsil of year 2001- 2002

Combination Type	Crops Combination	No. of Villages	Area	Total Area (%)
			Hectares	
Two Crop Combination	TP/B/W/FC/J	6	3988	3.93
Three Crop Combination	B/TP/J/O/F/FC/TV/S	27	33681	33.15
Four Crop Combination	J/TP/B/O/FC	15	19697	19.39
Five Crop Combination	J/TV/TP/FC/O/B/S	12	7811.4	7.69
Six Crop Combination	J/B/TP/TV/FC/O/S	19	9820.1	9.67
Seven Crop Combination	J/TP/TV/B/O/FC/W	7	4383.7	4.31
Eight Crop Combination	J/TP/W/FC/O/TV/S/B	6	2819.35	2.77
Eleven Crop Combination	S/FC/B/J/W/TP/TV/O/F/SP/FL	1	637.5	0.63
Twelve Crop Combination	J/O/B/TP/FC/TV/F/W/S/TOS/SP/FL	15	18762.06	18.46
Total		108	101600.11	100

TV- Total Vegetable Crops, TP- Total Pulses, B-Bajara, FL-Flower Crops, TOS- Total Oil Seed, W-Wheat, FC -Fodder Crop, S- Sugarcane, F-Fruit Crop, J-Jowar, SP- Spices, O – Onion.

Crop Combination in Shirur Tahsil of year 20011- 2012

Combination Type	Crops Combination	No. of Villages	Area	Total Area (%)
			(Hect)	
Two Crop Combination	TP/B/W/FC	6	6505	6.73
Three Crop Combination	W/TP/FC/B/O	7	5052	5.22
Four Crop Combination	TP/B/J/TV/S/FC/O	18	18223.51	18.84
Five Crop Combination	J/TV/TP/FC/O/B/S/W/F	13	11707.9	12.11
Six Crop Combination	J/B/TP/TV/FC/O/S/FL/W/F	22	13174.6	13.62
Seven Crop Combination	J/TP/TV/B/O/FC/W/S/F	19	19557.85	20.22
Eight Crop Combination	J/TP/W/FC/O/TV/S/B/F	7	4721.85	4.88
Nine Crop Combination	S/FC/B/J/W/TP/TV/O/F/SP/FL	2	1312.19	1.36
Twelve Crop Combination	J/O/B/TP/FC/TV/F/W/S/TOS/SP/FL	14	16460.8	17.02
Total		108	96715.7	100

Result and Discussion

All the Twelve types of crop combinations have been identified during 2001-2 to 2011-12 for Shirur Tahsil. The villages and area under each crop combination are shown in the above tables.

Two crop combination

This combination was only identified in Pabal circle and Nhavara circle during 2001-2002. Except Shirur Circle and Shikrapur Circle two crop combination is not found at any place in 2001-2, 2011-12. The major crops are Wheat, Total pulses Bajara, Fodder crop and Jowar crops in this combination. In 2001-2 two crop combination is found in area hecters 3988, and area in 3.93 percent. In 2011-12 2 two crop combination is hecters 6505, and area in 6.73 percent. Such as Babulasar Bk., Pimpalsuti, Inamgoan, Kahnnur Mesai, Malthan and Chincholi Morachi.etc villages.

Three crop combination

The dominant crops in this combination are Bajara, total Pulses, Jowar, Onion, Fodder crop, Total vegetable, and Sugarcane. Found in various villages. The area of this

combination reduced in 2000-01 (33.15 percent). And 2011-12 in which seven villages area in 5052 hectors, and 5.22 Present.

Four crop combination

The area of this combination was reduced in 2000-01 (19.39 percent). And 2011-12 in which 18 village's area in 18223 hectors and 18.84 at Present it. Is found in Pabal, Shikrapur, Shirur, and Nahavra Circle. Such as Shindodi, Nimone, Gunat, Nirvi, Nagargaon is the Nahavra Circle.

Five crop combination

Five crop combinations was found 2001-2 in which 12 villages dominantly were from Nahavra circle, Pabal Circle, Shikrapur Circle. The dominant crops in this combination are Bajara, Total pulses, Total Vegetables, Sugarcane, Wheat, Jowar, Onion, Fodder crop, and flowers found in various villages. The area of this combination reduced in 2000-01 (7.69 percent). And 2011-12 in which 13 villages area in 11707.90 hectors and 12.11 at Present it.

Six Crop Combinations

Six crop combinations was found 2001-2 in which 19 villages dominantly were from Shirur Circle Such as Pimparkhed, Chandoh, Fakate, Nimgaon Dude, Aamdabad etc. Pabal Circle in a not due to six crop combination and rarely found in Nahavra circle, Shikrapur Circle.

Seven Crop Combination

The crops in this combination are Bajara, Total pulses, Total Vegetable, Sugarcane, Jowar, Onion, and Fodder crop found in various villages. The area of this combination was reduced in 2000-01 (4.31 percent) and increased in 2011-12 in which 19 villages area in 19557.85 hectors and 13.62 present.

Eight Crop Combination

The crops in this combination are Bajara, Total pulses, Total Vegetable, Sugarcane, Jowar, Onion, Fodder crop, and Wheat. The area of this combination is reduced in 2000-01 (2.77 percent). And 2011-12, It was found in 4721.85 hectares (4.88 percent) in seven villages from Shirur circle Nahavra circle

Nine Crop Combination

The crops in this combination are Bajara, Total pulses, Total Vegetable, Sugarcane, Jowar, Onion, Flowers, Fodder crop, and Wheat. The area of this combination reduced in 2011-12 (1.36 percent). And 1312.19 area in hectors.

Eleven Crop Combination

This is combination was not found in Pabal Circle, Shirur Circle and Nahavra Circle in a not found eleven crop combination, the crops in this combination are Bajara, Total pulses, Total Vegetable,

Sugarcane, Jowar, Onion, Flowers, Fodder crop, Fruit, Spices and Wheat found in Koregaon Bhima.

Twelve Crop Combination

This crop combination are Bajara, Total pulses, Total Vegetable, Sugarcane, Jowar, Onion, Total Oil Seed, Fodder crop, and wheat found in various villages. The area of this combination is reduced in 2000-01 (18.47percent). And in 2011-12, it was found in 14 village's area in 16460 hectors and 17.02 present.

Conclusion

The crop combination method is tool for sustainable agriculture development. In agriculture, multiple cropping is the practice of growing two or more crops in the same piece of land during a single growing season. It is a form of polyculture. All Twelve types of crop combinations have been identified during 2001-2 to 2011-12 for Shirur Tahsil. The 12 crop combination area is highly identified in cropping pattern because of the number of favorable conditions for these crops from the above observation. It is clear that there is a tendency of specialization of 5 major crops i.e. Sugarcane, Fodder crops, Onion, Jawar and Total pulses. The development in irrigation facilities, soil productivity, skill of farmers, using the modern techniques in agricultural land and based on demand and supply of markets will change the existing cropping pattern.

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